

PERCEIVED EFFECTS OF EDUCATIONAL GAME ON THE ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE AMONG EDUCATION STUDENTS

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Perceived Effects of Educational Game on the Academic Performance among Education Students

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Abstract

This study aimed to determine the perceived effects of educational games on academic performance among education students. The respondents of this study were limited only to one-hundred twenty-seven (127) education students from first-year to third-year level in Khadijah Mohammad Islamic Academy (KMIA). The instrument used was adapted from the study of Bicen and Kocakoyun (2018). The data gathered was statistically analyzed, interpreted, and validated. The findings revealed that the respondents' age ranged between 18 to 25 years old and all of them had used Quizizz application. The finding showed that there was a significant relationship between the profile and the perception of respondents about the educational game application. It can be concluded that the educational game affected the academic performance of the respondents. It was recommended that future researchers must conduct similar studies in a wider scope or explore how the individuals' academic performance was involved in using educational games. For future researchers, the study highlighted the need for an in-depth exploration of the factors influencing the effectiveness of educational games, considering not only demographic variables but also individual preferences and sensitivities.

Keywords: *perceived effects, educational game, academic performance, education students*

Introduction

As technology continues to evolve, educational games have become increasingly prevalent in classrooms and informal learning environments. They blend entertainment with educational content, offering students a unique and interactive way to acquire knowledge and develop skills. Educational games are known to boost student engagement. Unlike traditional teaching methods, these games are designed to be fun, captivating, and immersive. As a result, students often become more motivated to participate actively in their learning, which can lead to increased attentiveness and retention of information. There are a lot more advantages to educational games. The use of technology in the classroom has made it possible to create and utilize a wider variety of instructional games for a wider range of disciplines. Educational games come in many forms and modalities and can be beneficial to students of all ages.

One of the big problems faced by teachers from different subject areas in the 21st century is student engagement. Most learners prefer to have an engaging and enjoyable learning process. However, it is essential to consider that the perceived effects of educational games can vary among students. Factors like game design, subject matter, and individual preferences play a significant role in determining how effective these games are in different contexts. Some students may find them highly beneficial, while others may not respond as positively. It is important to know how educational games can help to enhance student's motivation and learning perceptions towards educational games (Basuki & Hidayati, 2019).

Technology has affected society and its surroundings in many ways, one of which is education (Bicen & Kocakoyun, 2018). Education as part of culture is a means of transmitting values and ideas for everyone to participate in the transformation of values for the progress of the nation and state. Along with the times, the world of education is also experiencing rapid development, thus demanding changes that can adapt to the dynamic demands that are developing. One of the popular digital educational games used is Quizizz. According to similarweb.com's 2021 data analysis, the Quizizz website is rated eighth among scientific and education websites in terms of visits. With the help of this free gamified online quiz application, students may practice on PCs, tablets, and cellphones by answering questions. With appealing graphic elements, it can produce a multiplayer game, which is an engaging exercise for students (Mei et al., 2018).

The purpose of this study was to determine the perceived effect of educational games on academic performance among students. The impact of this research is to keep the learners engaged as it focuses on social learning and makes it fun. Teachers could incorporate it into their lessons as part of their assessment.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the perceived effect of educational game on the academic performance among education students from 1st year, 2nd year, and 3rd year under 1st semester in the Academic Year 2023-2024 in Khadijah Mohammad Islamic Academy. Specifically, this study aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. sex; and
 - 1.3. year level?
2. What is the perception of respondents about the educational game application?

3. What is the academic performance of the respondents as to their final average?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the demographic profile and the perceived effects of educational games?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the perceived effects of educational games and the academic performance of the respondents?
6. Which of the perceived effects of educational games and demographic profiles significantly predict the academic performance of the respondents?
7. What action plan on educational game can be designed based on the findings of the study.

Methodology

Research Design

In this study, the researcher used descriptive-correlational research design to achieve the purpose of the study. It is a type of research design that tried to explain the relationship between two or more variables without making any claims about cause and effect. This study also employed a correlation research design since it investigated the relationship between the perceived effects of educational games and the academic performance of the learners.

Respondents

The respondents in this study were students who had used Quizizz in their learning which are the education students. They were exposed to educational games compared to other courses in the KMIA school. From the 1st year, they have 70 students in total, from the 2nd year, with 81 students, and from the 3rd year, with 105 students under the 1st semester of the academic year 2023-2024. There were 256 education students in the total population and only 127 of the said total population were needed as respondents and that was only fifty percent.

Furthermore, the researcher utilized stratified random sampling in every year level. Stratified random sampling is a sampling technique in which the population is divided into subgroups or strata based on certain characteristics that are relevant to the research. These strata are then used to ensure that the sample drawn for the study is representative of the entire population concerning those characteristics. The goal of stratified random sampling is to increase the precision and representativeness of the sample, especially when there is variability in the population (Nickolas, 2021).

Table 1. *Distribution of Respondents by Year level*

<i>Year level</i>	<i>Total Number of Students</i>	<i>Total Number of Respondents</i>
1st year	70	35
2nd year	81	40
3rd year	105	52
Total	256	127

Instruments

This study had used an adapted questionnaire to gather the necessary data. The survey questionnaire was adapted by Bicen, H., and Kocakoyun, S. (2018) in their study perceptions of students for the gamification approach. The survey questionnaire had two parts: the first part was the respondents' profile, and the second part was the 27 items about the perceived effect of educational games. The survey checklist used a four-point Likert scale (strongly agree, agree, disagree, and strongly disagree). The student's highest positive answer was associated with a score of 4, while the lowest was 1.

On the other hand, the researcher made some minor changes to the adapted questionnaire that was used as an instrument of the study. The researcher also underwent pilot testing before being used as the final instrument. The reliability coefficient of the study during the pilot testing was 0.706 which meant the adapted questionnaire was reliable.

Procedure

The researcher wrote a letter for the School President requesting permission to conduct a study in order to acquire the data. Finally, the proponent also sent letters to the first- through third-year education students who participated in the study as responders. Included with the survey questionnaire was a consent letter for the respondents.

Upon its approval, the researcher administered the questionnaire to the respondents during their convenience time. It was distributed in the three-year levels with the same instructor that uses Quizizz as their educational games but in different subject areas in professional education. The researcher made sure that the 127 respondents were all familiar and used Quizizz because the instructor made them play again as their motivational activity days before the study was conducted in the school.

The respondents answered the given questionnaire with the assistance of the researcher. They were given enough time to answer and then retrieved after they were done answering. An assurance was given that it would be confidential. Moreover, the researcher asked permission from the instructor who used Quizizz game as their educational game in the area of professional education about the grades of the learners as of the 1st semester. This served as the academic performance. The data gathering procedures took four days to finish

the survey in the school.

Data Analysis

The data gathered in this research was interpreted using the following tools:

For problems 1 and 3, frequency and percentage were used in describing the demographic profile in terms of age, sex, and year level and also their academic performance.

For problem 2, the weighted mean was used in describing the perceived effect of educational games.

For problems 4 and 5, regression analysis was used to determine the significant relationship between the demographic profile and the perceived effect of educational games and the significant relationship between the demographic profile and the academic performance of the learners.

Results and Discussion

This section contains the presentations, analysis, and interpretation of the acquired data. In order to simplify the discussion, the researcher provided tables to summarize the collective data from the respondents.

Problem 1: What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of age, sex, and year level?

Table 1. Age of the Respondents

Age (in years)	Frequency	Percentage (%)
17-19	32	25.2
20-22	64	50.4
23-25	25	19.7
26-27	6	4.7
Total	127	100.0

Note: Mean (SD) = 21.13 (2.14)

Table 1 presents the age distribution of the respondents in a survey, detailing the frequency and percentage of individuals within specific age brackets. The majority of respondents fell within the 20-22 age group, constituting 50.4% of the sample, followed by the 17-19 age group at 25.2%. The 23-25 age range accounted for 19.7% of the respondents, while individuals aged 26-27 made up the smallest proportion at 4.7%. The mean age of the respondents was 21.13 years, with a standard deviation of 2.14, providing a measure of the dispersion around the mean.

This result suggested that the survey primarily captured the perspectives of individuals in their late teens and early twenties, with a relatively homogeneous distribution around the mean age. The standard deviation indicated a moderate level of variability, implying that the age range was not excessively diverse. As it was mentioned by Individuals in their late teens and early twenties were often more technologically savvy and comfortable with digital platforms, including educational games. Whereas, it was mentioned by Zimmerling, et al (2019) that individuals in their late teens and early twenties were often more technologically savvy and comfortable with digital platforms, including educational games.

Table 2. Sex of the Respondents

Sex	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Male	6	4.7
Female	121	95.3
Total	127	100.0

Table 2 shows the gender distribution among the survey respondents, outlining both the frequency and percentage of individuals based on their sex. The majority of respondents were identified as females, comprising 95.3% of the total sample. In contrast, males constituted a small minority, representing only 4.7% of the respondents. This gender imbalance may have implications for the generalizability of the study findings, as the male subgroup was relatively underrepresented. According to the research of Escobar Fandiño et al. (2019), the research about the motivation in Quizizz based on gender is very limited. Moreover, it was also mentioned by Feng et al. (2018) that support this result, they stated that the students' motivation can affect by their gender; females have higher achievements in learning than males.

Table 3. Year Level of the Respondents

Year Level	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1st year	39	30.7
2nd year	41	32.3
3rd year	47	37.0
Total	127	100.0

Table 3 illustrates the distribution of respondents based on their respective year levels, presenting both the frequency and percentage within each academic year. Among the respondents, the highest percentage was found in the 3rd year, constituting 37.0% of the total

sample. The 2nd year followed closely behind, accounting for 32.3%, while the 1st year represented 30.7%. This distribution provided insights into the composition of the surveyed population in terms of their academic progression. The finding suggested a relatively balanced distribution across the three academic years, with a slight predominance of students in their 3rd year. A wider review of the studies showed that the application of educational games was beneficial in several ways for students in secondary education and higher education (Curto-Prieto et al., 2019).

Problem 2: What is the perception of respondents about the educational game application?

The analysis of respondents' perceptions about the educational game application Quizizz revealed an overall positive attitude toward the platform. Participants expressed high motivation levels, as indicated by positive responses to items such as feeling motivated (Mean=3.22, SD=0.70), enjoying its use (Mean=3.36, SD=0.56), and being motivated to achieve high rankings (Mean=3.29, SD=0.66). The moderate standard deviations suggested a degree of variability in the extent of agreement among respondents, emphasizing the need to recognize individual differences in motivational responses.

Table 4. Perception of Respondents about the Educational Game Application

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
1. I feel motivated when using educational games via Quizizz	3.22	0.70	Agree
2. Colorful display on Quizizz eases me in remembering the material.	3.28	0.56	Agree
3. Quizizz application can be used easily.	2.97	0.62	Agree
4. Doing quizzes through the Quizizz application is simpler and easier than taking quizzes on paper	2.98	0.70	Agree
5. My classroom engagement has been improved by using Quizizz.	2.94	0.69	Agree
6. It's enjoyable to use Quizizz.	3.36	0.56	Agree
7. I'm motivated to get rankings and the highest scores when using Quizizz.	3.29	0.66	Agree
8. Quizizz can increase my understanding of learning material.	3.25	0.58	Agree
9. I can focus better using Quizizz.	2.91	0.64	Agree
10. It promotes social interaction	2.92	0.70	Agree
11. It encourages active participation	3.13	0.59	Agree
12. Quizizz is a better learning media for me than doing exercises on paper	2.93	0.69	Agree
13. Quizizz promotes knowledge retention	3.17	0.55	Agree
14. Each question I correctly answer improves my self-confidence	3.27	0.64	Agree
15. The background music is destructing	2.70	0.80	Agree
16. I did not get bored in the lesson at all	3.04	0.62	Agree
17. Gamification encourages active participation	3.01	0.60	Agree
18. I feel bad if I am unsuccessful when a game method is applied	2.87	0.72	Agree
19. Each question I correctly answer improves my self-confidence	3.23	0.67	Agree
20. Game-based learning methods increase classroom competition	3.11	0.61	Agree
21. The formation of a competitive environment increases my motivation in the classroom	3.07	0.62	Agree
22. Using a gamification method for group work in crowded classes increases the level of competition	2.98	0.65	Agree
23. Gamification enables me to learn difficult topics while having fun	3.08	0.69	Agree
24. The use of Quizizz in the classroom encourages learners	3.16	0.65	Agree
25. The active use of Quizizz builds student courage to participate in activities.	3.30	0.62	Agree
26. Quizizz improves the rapid-thinking abilities of students	3.22	0.62	Agree
27. Lesson performed with Quizizz enable permanent learning compared to learning memory in traditional classroom environment	2.98	0.65	Agree
Total Measure	3.09	.30	Agree

Note: 1.00-1.49, Strongly Disagree; 1.50-2.49, Disagree; 2.50-3.49, Agree; 3.50-4.00, Strongly Agree

In terms of usability and accessibility, Quizizz was generally perceived as user-friendly, with respondents finding it easy to use (Mean=2.97, SD=0.62). The moderate standard deviation implied that while the majority found it easy to use, there were variations in individual experiences. Educators should consider providing additional support for users who may find certain aspects less user-friendly to ensure a more inclusive learning environment. Positive perceptions related to learning efficacy were reflected in high mean scores for indicators such as improving understanding of learning material (Mean=3.25, SD=0.58) and promoting knowledge retention (Mean=3.17, SD=0.55). The relatively low standard deviations suggested a consistent agreement among respondents, indicating a shared positive view on the educational effectiveness of Quizizz.

The findings also highlighted the positive influence of Quizizz on the classroom environment. Students agreed that Quizizz improved classroom engagement (Mean=2.94, SD=0.69), encouraged active participation (Mean=3.13, SD=0.59), and fostered a competitive environment (Mean=3.07, SD=0.62).

While standard deviations indicated some variability in responses, educators could leverage Quizizz to create a more dynamic and participatory classroom environment, recognizing that individual responses might vary.

Concerns about distractions were evident in the slightly lower mean score for background music (Mean=2.70, SD=0.80). The higher

standard deviation suggested greater variability in responses, indicating that opinions on the impact of background music may differ widely. Developers and educators should carefully design and implement audio features in gamified platforms, considering the diverse preferences and sensitivities of students.

Thus, the analysis of Quizizz's impact on motivation, usability, learning efficacy, and classroom dynamics provided valuable insights for educators. By recognizing both overall positive trends and individual differences in experiences and preferences among students, educators could make informed decisions about incorporating gamification into their teaching strategies, creating a more engaging and inclusive learning environment.

Understanding perceptions was important in improving the quality of learning delivery and getting along well with the learning tools used. Therefore, it was essential to determine students' perceptions, to encourage the use of gamification dynamics in the instructional process (Çakiroğlu et al., 2016).

Studies had shown that digital game-based learning had a positive impact on learners' motivation, attitude engagement, and performance (Tapingkae et al., 2020). The findings of Karpouzis (2017) mentioned several experiences in research on game-based learning applications to increase student engagement, and students have to measure the effectiveness of games and education. When some games were added to the learning, many students participated, and became more active and interested in studying.

Problem 3: What is the academic performance of the respondents as to their final average?

Table 5. *Academic Performance of the Students*

<i>Academic Performance</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
Outstanding (90-100)	24	18.9
Very Satisfactory (85-89)	100	78.7
Satisfactory (80-84)	3	2.4
Fairly Satisfactory (75-79)	0	0.0
Did Not Meet Expectation (60-74)	0	0.0
Total	127	100.0

Note: Mean (SD) = 87.86 (1.90)

Table 5 provides a detailed breakdown of the academic performance of the surveyed students, presenting frequencies and percentages within specific grade ranges. Notably, the majority of students fell within the "Very Satisfactory" category, with 78.7% achieving grades in the range of 85-89. A smaller proportion of students, 18.9%, achieved an "Outstanding" performance with grades ranging from 90-100. Only a minimal percentage, 2.4%, received a "Satisfactory" rating in the 80-84 range. Importantly, no students fell within the "Fairly Satisfactory" or "Did Not Meet Expectation" categories, indicating a notably high overall level of academic achievement in the sample. The mean academic performance score of 87.86 with a standard deviation of 1.90 further reinforced the positive academic standing of the respondents. This tight standard deviation suggested a relatively homogeneous distribution of grades, indicating consistency in academic performance among the surveyed students. The high mean score aligned with the predominantly positive perceptions of Quizizz, as discussed in previous analyses.

According to Setyaningsih (2022), the game significantly enhanced student performance and learning because it increased students' interest in education. As it was also mentioned by Zhao (2019) that the students stated that Quizizz had a positive effect on the students' learning experiences.

Problem 4: Is there a significant relationship between the demographic profile and the perceived effect of educational games?

Table 6. *Regression Analysis of Relating Perceived Effect of Educational Games by the Demographic Profile of the Respondents*

<i>Predictor</i>	<i>Estimate</i>	<i>SE</i>	<i>Standardized Estimate</i>	<i>t-value</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Remarks</i>
Age	0.04	0.01	0.26	2.435*	0.016	Significant
Sex (Female)	0.05	0.13	0.16	0.384	0.701	Not significant
Year Level						
1st year	Ref					
2nd year	0.11	0.07	0.37	1.659	0.100	Not significant
3rd year	0.03	0.08	0.10	0.397	0.692	Not significant

Note: Adjusted R² = 0.057 ANOVA for Regression: F=2.92, p=0.024 *significant at 0.05 level

Table 6 presents the results of a regression analysis examining the relationship between the perceived effect of educational games, as measured by the respondents, and their demographic profiles. The analysis included age, sex, and year level as predictors. Notably, the age variable demonstrated a significant relationship with the perceived effect of educational games, with an estimate of 0.04, a standardized estimate of 0.26, a t-value of 2.435, and a p-value of 0.016. This suggested that as the age of the respondent increases, there was a positive and statistically significant impact on their perceived effectiveness of educational games.

On the other hand, the regression analysis did not find a significant relationship between the perceived effect of educational games and the sex or year level of the respondents. The estimate for females was 0.05, with a standardized estimate of 0.16 and a p-value of 0.701, indicating that gender did not significantly influence the perceived effect of educational games. Similarly, the year-level predictors

(2nd year and 3rd year) did not show statistically significant associations, as evidenced by p-values of 0.100 and 0.692, respectively.

The adjusted R² of 0.057 indicated that the model explained a small but significant proportion of the variance in the perceived effect of educational games among respondents. The ANOVA for regression yielded an F-value of 2.92 with a p-value of 0.024, further supporting the overall significance of the model. The implications of these findings were twofold. First, the significant relationship between age and the perceived effect of educational games suggested that older respondents tended to have a more positive perception of the impact of these games on their learning experiences. This insight could guide educators in tailoring gamified learning strategies to different age groups, recognizing the potential variations in effectiveness. Second, while sex and year level did not emerge as significant predictors, their inclusion in the analysis contributed to a comprehensive understanding of the diverse factors influencing perceptions of educational games among students. Educators can leverage these insights to inform the design and implementation of gamified learning approaches that resonated with students across various socio-demographic profiles.

According to the study of Serrano (2019) the gamification in education was an innovative, modern way to increase engagement and motivation in learners of all ages, higher to lower, both in and out classroom setting. Also, individuals in their late teens and early twenties were often more technologically savvy and comfortable with digital platforms, including educational games (Zimmerling, 2019).

Problem 5: Is there a significant relationship between the demographic profile and the academic performance of the respondents?

Table 7. *Regression Analysis of Relating Academic Performance by the Demographic Profile of the Respondents*

Predictor	Estimate	SE	Standardized Estimate	t-value	p-value	Remarks
Age	-0.12	0.10	-0.13	-1.194	0.235	Not significant
Sex (Female)	-0.58	0.82	-0.30	-0.707	0.481	Not significant
Year Level						
1st year	Ref					
2nd year	-0.28	0.43	-0.15	-0.640	0.523	Not significant
3rd year	0.61	0.50	0.32	1.237	0.218	Not significant

Note: Adjusted R² = 0.006 ANOVA for Regression: F=1.20, p=0.315 not significant at 0.05 level

Table 7 displays the results of a regression analysis examining the relationship between the academic performance of respondents and their demographic profiles, including age, sex (with females as the reference category), and year level. The analysis revealed that none of the predictors significantly influenced academic performance.

Specifically, the age variable exhibited a non-significant relationship with academic performance, with an estimate of -0.12, a standardized estimate of -0.13, a t-value of -1.194, and a p-value of 0.235. This suggested that, within the context of this study, age did not play a statistically significant role in predicting academic performance.

Similarly, the sex of the respondents (with females as the reference category) did not demonstrate a significant association with academic performance. The estimate for females was -0.58, with a standardized estimate of -0.30, and a p-value of 0.481, indicating that gender was not a statistically significant predictor of academic performance.

The year-level predictors (2nd year and 3rd year) also did not show significant associations with academic performance, as evidenced by p-values of 0.523 and 0.218, respectively. The adjusted R² of 0.006 indicated that the model explained only a small proportion of the variance in academic performance among respondents. The ANOVA for regression yielded an F-value of 1.20 with a p-value of 0.315, further supporting the overall non-significance of the model.

These results implied that, in this particular sample, demographic factors such as age, gender, and academic year did not serve as significant predictors of academic performance. While this study provided valuable insights within its specific context, educators should consider additional factors and individualized approaches when understanding and addressing the diverse influences on students' academic achievements. The lack of significant associations suggested that other factors beyond the ones examined in this analysis may have a more pronounced impact on academic performance among the surveyed students.

Moreover, it was possible that the educational games have a consistent impact across different year levels, leading to similar levels of academic performance improvement for students at all grade levels. If this is the case, the year-level variable may not be a significant predictor because the effect of educational games is consistent across different grades (Belova et al., 2020).

Problem 6: Which of the perceptions about educational games and socio-demographic profiles significantly predict the academic performance of the respondents?

Table 8 presents the results of a regression analysis aiming to understand the relationship between academic performance, demographic profiles, and the perceived impact of educational games among respondents. The predictors included the perceived effect of educational games, age, sex (with females as the reference category), and year level.

Surprisingly, the perceived effect of educational games did not show a significant relationship with academic performance, as indicated

by an estimate of 0.42, a standardized estimate of 0.07, a t-value of 0.717, and a p-value of 0.475. This suggested that, within the context of this study, students' perceptions of the effectiveness of educational games did not significantly predict their academic performance.

Table 8. *Regression Analysis of Relating Academic Performance by the Demographic Profile and Perceived Educational Games of the Respondents*

Predictor	Estimate	SE	Standardized Estimate	t-value	p-value	Remarks
Educational Games	0.42	0.59	0.07	0.717	0.475	Not significant
Age	-0.13	0.10	-0.15	-1.318	0.190	Not significant
Sex (Female)	-0.60	0.82	-0.31	-0.730	0.467	Not significant
Year Level						
1st year	Ref					
2nd year	-0.32	0.44	-0.17	-0.738	0.462	Not significant
3rd year	0.60	0.50	0.32	1.208	0.229	Not significant

Similarly, age, sex, and year level also did not emerge as significant predictors of academic performance. The estimate for age is -0.13, with a standardized estimate of -0.15 and a p-value of 0.190. The estimate for females was -0.60, with a standardized estimate of -0.31 and a p-value of 0.467. Year-level predictors (2nd year and 3rd year) did not show significant associations, with p-values of 0.462 and 0.229, respectively.

The adjusted R² of 0.006 once again indicated that the model explained only a small proportion of the variance in academic performance among respondents. The ANOVA for regression yielded an F-value of 1.20 with a p-value of 0.315, further supporting the overall non-significance of the model.

These results suggested that, in this particular sample, the perceived effect of educational games, along with demographic factors, did not play a significant role in predicting academic performance. Educators and researchers should consider exploring additional factors that may influence the complex dynamics between students' perceptions of educational tools and their academic achievements. Educational games must be carefully designed in order to engage and motivate students.

From the study of Setyaningsih (2022) he mentioned that the game significantly enhanced student performance and learning because it increased students' interest in education. However, in contrast to the finding of Abras (2018) saying that studies have not found consistent evidence that games would affect academic performance.

Conclusions

Based on the findings, the following conclusions were drawn.

This study concluded that Quizizz, as an educational game application, enjoyed widespread positive reception among surveyed students, fostering high levels of motivation and engagement. The platform's perceived user-friendliness and efficacy in improving understanding and promoting knowledge retention contributed to its positive impact on the classroom environment. However, the variation in individual experiences and concerns about distractions, such as background music, underscored the importance of tailoring educational technology to accommodate diverse preferences and sensitivities.

In terms of academic performance, the study found an exceptionally high level of achievement among surveyed students, with the majority falling within the top two performance categories. This suggested a generally high academic proficiency within the sampled group, reflecting positively on the overall educational environment.

The analysis of the relationship between the perceived effect of educational games and demographic profiles revealed age as a significant factor influencing how students perceived the effectiveness of such tools. In contrast, gender and academic year level did not significantly impact these perceptions. These findings highlighted the importance of considering age-related factors when designing and implementing educational games, and recognizing the nuanced preferences of students across different age groups.

However, when exploring the predictors of academic performance, including demographic profiles and the perceived impact of educational games, none of these factors emerged as significant predictors. This implied that factors beyond age, gender, academic year level, and perceived game effectiveness played a more substantial role in determining academic outcomes. These results underscored the intricate interplay of various factors influencing academic performance, signaling the need for a comprehensive understanding of the complex dynamics involved in student success.

Thus, this study contributed valuable insights into the positive reception of Quizizz, the high academic achievement among surveyed students, and the positive influence of age on perceptions of educational game effectiveness. While these findings shed light on certain aspects of the educational landscape, the intricate nature of academic performance suggested that multiple factors did not capture in this analysis, contribute to students' success in their academic endeavors.

Based on the conclusions drawn, the following recommendations were formulated:

For curriculum planners and school administrators, the positive reception of Quizizz among students underscored the potential benefits

of integrating gamified learning tools into the curriculum. Considering the platform's ability to motivate learners and enhance classroom engagement, curriculum planners may explore incorporating similar educational game applications strategically across various subjects.

Furthermore, administrators could invest in training sessions for teachers to ensure effective implementation, leveraging the positive impact of such tools on the overall learning experience.

Teachers must recognize the varied experiences and concerns about distractions, particularly background music. They should tailor their use of Quizizz to accommodate diverse preferences. Providing additional support to students who may find certain aspects less user-friendly can enhance inclusivity and ensure that all learners can benefit from the educational game. Moreover, educators should leverage the platform's positive impact on learning efficacy and classroom engagement to create dynamic and participatory learning environments.

Learners must be encouraged by the positive perceptions of Quizizz, and are urged to actively engage with the platform and communicate their preferences and concerns to educators. This collaboration can foster a more interactive and customized learning experience. Additionally, students should recognize the potential distractions, such as background music, and communicate their impact on the learning process, facilitating a more effective use of the platform.

For future researchers, the study highlighted the need for an in-depth exploration of the factors influencing the effectiveness of educational games, considering not only demographic variables but also individual preferences and sensitivities. Further research could delve into the specific elements of gamified learning tools that contribute to motivation and engagement, providing a more nuanced understanding for educators and administrators.

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